

GENDER-BASED INEQUALITY IN THE PRIVATE SECTOR IN GEORGIA

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ABSTRACT

Gender-based wage inequality constitutes one of the most critical socio-economic challenges in contemporary labor markets. Despite the existence of legislation in Georgia aimed at promoting gender equality, as well as the country's commitment to international obligations, available statistical data reveal a significant disparity in the economic status of women and men.

The purpose of this study is to identify the scale and underlying factors of gender inequality in the private sector, as well as to assess the effectiveness of legal and institutional mechanisms. The research employs a mixed methodology: a quantitative survey (185 respondents) and in-depth interviews (6 participants). The results confirm that women are often concentrated in low-paid positions, their education is less likely to translate into career advancement, and promotion processes usually favor men. Interview data further demonstrate that discriminatory practices manifest both at the recruitment stage and within workplace environments and promotion processes.

The findings indicate that gender inequality in Georgia is systemic in nature, and its mitigation requires both stronger public policies and a transformation of organizational culture.

Keywords: gender inequality, wage gap, private sector, labor market, glass ceiling.

Introduction

Gender inequality in the labor market remains one of the major challenges both globally and locally. According to international studies, the economic positions of women and men differ significantly—wages, career opportunities, and working conditions are often distributed unequally by gender (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2022). Such inequality is not only a violation of social justice but also one of the key obstacles to a country's economic and social development (World Bank, 2021).

In Georgia, as in other post-Soviet countries, the problem is particularly evident in the private sector. Official data show that in 2023 the gender pay gap stood at 20.9%, considerably higher than the European Union average (12%; Eurostat, 2023). These figures indicate that Georgia's labor market fails to provide equal pay and equal opportunities for both genders. Moreover, women are often concentrated in low-paid sectors and positions, while their representation in managerial roles remains minimal.

Examining gender inequality solely through the lens of social justice is insufficient. The underutilization of women's professional potential directly impedes national economic development. World Bank research highlights that in countries where the gap in labor force participation between women and men decreases, economic productivity rises significantly (World Bank, 2021). Therefore, gender equality must be regarded not only as a matter of rights but also as an economic imperative.

Cultural and social stereotypes in Georgia play a particularly significant role, as women are commonly perceived as primarily responsible for family care and child-rearing. These traditional norms limit women's career development and create the so-called "glass ceiling"—an invisible barrier that prevents women from reaching high-level positions (Morrison, White, & Van

Velsor, 1987). As a result, despite formal equality, informal barriers continue to restrict women's professional opportunities.

Thus, gender inequality in Georgia should not be viewed as an individual or incidental problem, but rather as a systemic and structural challenge that requires both policy reform and changes in organizational practice.

The aim of this study was to identify the scale, underlying factors, and institutional mechanisms of gender inequality in the private sector, as well as to assess the legal and organizational framework. Based on this aim, the following research questions were formulated:

- To what extent does the gender pay gap manifest in Georgia's private sector?
- What role do education and qualifications play in the career advancement of women and men?
- How significant are institutional and cultural barriers (the "glass ceiling") for women's professional development?

The following hypotheses were developed:

H1: Women in the private sector are concentrated in low - paid positions, while men are more likely to hold higher-paid roles.

H2: Education and qualifications translate more effectively into higher-paid positions for men than for women.

H3: The "glass ceiling" effect systematically restricts women's advancement into senior managerial roles.

Literature Review

Gender inequality in the labor market has been extensively studied both in Western and post-Soviet academic contexts. Theoretical models and empirical research seek to explain the causes of wage disparities, occupational segregation, and the "glass ceiling" effect.

Neoclassical theory argues that labor market differences are driven by individual decisions (Becker,

1993). According to this perspective, women invest less in education and careers due to family obligations, resulting in their overrepresentation in low-paid positions. However, numerous studies indicate that even when women and men have identical levels of education and experience, wage disparities persist (Rosenfeld & Spenner, 1992). A similar pattern was observed in Georgia: women's education translates less effectively into corresponding wages and positions, whereas for men this correlation is significantly stronger.

Institutional theory emphasizes that the labor market is not structurally neutral. Despite formal equality, informal norms and cultural stereotypes generate inequality (North, 1990). Charles and Grusky (2004) demonstrate that organizational culture associates "male" positions with high responsibility and "female" positions with lower pay. Findings from research conducted in Georgia—where women are concentrated mainly in lower-level managerial roles—directly support this theory.

Radical theory and the concept of the "glass ceiling" highlight invisible barriers that restrict women's upward mobility. Morrison, White, and Van Velsor (1987) argue that these barriers become particularly evident when women reach middle management but fail to progress to higher hierarchical levels. Cotter, Hermsen, Ovadia, and Vanneman (2001) add that the "glass ceiling" emerges even when promotion opportunities appear equal on paper, as women in practice remain less likely to receive actual promotions. In Georgia, women occupy only 2% of top managerial positions, perfectly illustrating this phenomenon.

International data reinforce this picture. According to an ILO (2022) report, women globally earn on average 20% less than men. Within the European Union, this gap averages 12% (Eurostat, 2023). Georgia's figure (20.9%) is considerably worse, highlighting the country's structural challenges. OECD (2021) studies show that pay transparency policies and mandatory gender audits significantly reduce inequality. For instance, the introduction of such regulations in Norway and Iceland led to a marked decrease in the gender pay gap.

UN Women's study *Employment and Gender in Georgia* (2022) indicates that women in Georgia are concentrated in the education and healthcare sectors, which are relatively low-paying. This trend fully aligns with the findings of the present research. Similarly, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2024) emphasizes the persistence of strong social stereotypes: women are still expected to prioritize family responsibilities, while men are expected to focus on careers.

Existing research largely portrays the general picture of gender inequality but pays insufficient attention to the specific dynamics of the private sector and its differences compared to the public sector. This gap is precisely what the present study aims to address, by focusing on the private sector—the sphere where inequality is most pronounced.

Methodology

The study employed a **mixed-methods approach**, integrating the collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data. Such an approach allows for capturing not only the statistical scale of gender inequality but also the deeper cultural and institutional factors driving this phenomenon.

As part of the quantitative component, an **online survey** was conducted with 185 employees (aged 18–65) working in both the private and public sectors. However, the analysis primarily focused on the private sector. The questionnaire included demographic information, perceptions of gender discrimination, and questions related to personal experiences.

The qualitative component consisted of **six in-depth interviews** with human resource managers, lawyers, and private sector employees. The goal of the interviews was to contextualize and interpret the quantitative data, particularly by reflecting on subjective experiences of gender-related barriers.

Quantitative data were analyzed using **descriptive statistics, t-tests, and ANOVA** in order to assess wage disparities between genders and to evaluate the role of education and qualifications in career advancement. Qualitative data were analyzed through **thematic analysis**, which enabled the identification of key themes and patterns related to discriminatory practices, promotion barriers, and institutional stereotypes. To ensure the **reliability** of the study, **methodological triangulation** was applied, meaning that quantitative and qualitative data were cross-validated against each other.

Nevertheless, the study has certain limitations. The sample size (N=185) is of medium scale and may not fully represent Georgia's labor market as a whole. Furthermore, the questionnaire structure did not allow for the detailed exploration of all sector-specific dynamics. Therefore, additional studies are needed for drawing more comprehensive conclusions on some aspects of the issue.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of quantitative data revealed a sharp wage disparity between women and men in the private sector. The majority of surveyed women reported an average monthly salary between 1,000–1,500 GEL, whereas a significant proportion of men earned over 3,000 GEL. This difference persisted even when respondents held identical positions.

Diagram 1. Distribution of salaries of women and men

This finding supports ILO's (2022) conclusion that the gender pay gap is systemic and cannot be explained solely by individual factors. According to neoclassical theory, wage disparities should be associated with education and career choices (Becker, 1993). However, the data indicate that education for women is less likely to translate into higher-paid positions.

Gender imbalance in managerial roles is particularly striking. Ten percent of men occupy senior management positions, while the share of women in such roles is only 2%. Conversely, women are twice as likely to be concentrated in lower-level managerial positions.

Table 1.

Distribution of managerial positions by gender

Position Held	Female	Male
Senior Manager	2%	10%
Middle Manager	20%	18%
Junior Manager	18%	7%
Other	17%	5%
Declined to Answer	1%	0%

This finding aligns with the “glass ceiling” phenomenon, which prevents women from ascending to higher hierarchical levels (Morrison, White, & Van Velsor, 1987; Cotter et al., 2001). As a result, despite qualifications and experience, women's advancement remains systematically constrained.

The analysis further revealed that men's educational attainment strongly correlates with wages (ANOVA: $p < .003$), whereas for women the relationship was weak. In practice, this means that women's education and qualifications do not consistently convert into economic capital.

This contradicts neoclassical theory, which posits that education and qualifications should have equivalent effects on earnings across genders. Instead, the results better support institutional theory, which highlights the role of informal structures—stereotypes and cultural norms—in sustaining inequality (North, 1990; Charles & Grusky, 2004).

In-depth interviews further highlighted discriminatory practices. Female candidates were frequently asked personal questions during job interviews—about family planning, the number of children, and balancing work with household responsibilities. Thirty-seven percent of women reported being asked questions about children, compared to only 12% of men.

This practice confirms institutional theory: despite formal equality, informal stereotypes (e.g., “women are less reliable employees because family obligations interfere with work”) restrict women's employment and career opportunities (Charles & Grusky, 2004).

Survey data also showed that 32% of women had never been promoted, whereas the majority of men had received multiple promotions. This discrepancy intensifies the “glass ceiling” effect and creates a risk of demotivation among women.

Diagram 2. Distribution of promotions and rewards by gender

Cotter et al. (2001) emphasize that the low frequency of promotions among women is one of the clearest indicators of structural barriers. Our findings strongly align with this theoretical argument.

Diagram 3. Distribution of benefits by gender

Furthermore, 65% of men reported feeling comfortable expressing their opinions during work meetings, compared to only 44% of women. This indicates that organizational culture amplifies men's voices more than women's. Similar tendencies were described in Kanter's (1977) classic study, which identified women's "lack of voice" as a manifestation of institutional discrimination.

Diagram 4. Comfort level in meetings by gender

The results demonstrate that gender inequality in Georgia's private sector cannot be explained solely by individual choices or personal responsibility. The findings directly contradict neoclassical theory, which assumes that labor markets are neutral and that differences stem from individual investments and preferences. In our data, women's education and qualifications fail to transform into the same levels of pay and career positions as men's. For example, while

men's education levels showed a strong positive correlation with wages, for women this link was weak or nonexistent. This indicates that education and professional development do not provide equal opportunities for women, undermining a central principle of neoclassical theory.

On the other hand, the findings strongly support institutional theory, which focuses on formal and informal institutions, cultural norms, and organizational practices. The prevalence of personal questions during

interviews, women's lower promotion rates, and their reduced comfort in expressing opinions at meetings clearly suggest that organizational environments restrict women's opportunities. These patterns are not unique to Georgia; Charles and Grusky (2004) describe similar mechanisms in Western countries, where occupational segregation is shaped by social norms and cultural expectations. Our study confirms this theory in the Georgian context, showing that institutional and cultural barriers are particularly entrenched.

In addition, the results fully illustrate radical theory and the "glass ceiling" phenomenon. Women's presence in only 2% of senior managerial positions demonstrates that their advancement is systematically blocked, despite qualifications and professional experience. Morrison et al. (1987) describe the "glass ceiling" as an invisible barrier that manifests precisely when women attempt to move from middle to higher levels of management. Our results confirm this phenomenon locally: women reach middle management but rarely advance further. These findings also align with Cotter et al. (2001), who stress that even when formal promotion opportunities appear equal, women remain systematically less likely to achieve actual advancement.

Georgia's figures are significantly worse than the EU average (Eurostat, 2023). OECD experience shows that pay transparency policies and mandatory gender audits can effectively reduce inequality (OECD, 2021). The absence of such mechanisms in Georgia is one of the key structural drivers of inequality.

In-depth interviews reinforced the quantitative findings, illustrating that gender discrimination in Georgia's labor market is multifaceted and systemic. Respondents highlighted several main areas:

- **Discrimination in recruitment.** Women frequently face both direct and indirect discriminatory practices. The most common example is being asked personal questions. One respondent noted: *"I experienced a situation where, after successfully passing the first stage of the interview, men were given preference at the second stage because it was assumed they would have more time and be more focused on the job..."* (Female, 36, private sector)

This confirms institutional theory, which suggests that informal norms and entrenched stereotypes restrict women's employment opportunities.

- **Unequal treatment in the workplace.** Discrimination does not end at the hiring stage—women face barriers throughout career development. As one respondent explained: *"Employers often question our leadership abilities simply because we are women... In the end, a man with less qualification was given the preference over me."* (Female, 33)

This example highlights the "glass ceiling": even with sufficient qualifications, women are systematically overlooked for promotions.

Barriers to career advancement and sectoral differences. Respondents noted that although promotions are formally available, women are less likely to receive them and are often excluded from senior man-

agement roles. The imbalance is particularly pronounced in the private sector, whereas public sector regulations provide partial safeguards.

- **Legal aspects.** Lawyers observed that women increasingly file lawsuits regarding discrimination; however, the legal burden of proof remains complex. One lawyer stated:

"Recently, women have become more vocal about these issues and more often take them to court... but proving discrimination legally is still very difficult."

(Male, 42, lawyer)

This finding underscores the weakness of existing legal mechanisms, which fail to provide effective protection in practice.

The qualitative evidence strengthens the statistical picture:

- Discrimination in recruitment violates the principle of "equal opportunity" and confirms institutional barriers.

- Low promotion rates and minimal female representation in leadership positions directly illustrate the "glass ceiling."

- Weaknesses in legal mechanisms demonstrate that formal norms in Georgia are insufficient to bring about real change in practice.

In sum, the findings confirm that gender discrimination in Georgia is not merely a statistical difference but an integral part of women's everyday professional experiences.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study revealed that gender inequality in Georgia's private sector is a systemic and multidimensional problem. Quantitative analysis demonstrated that women are concentrated in low-paid positions, while men are more likely to hold higher-paid jobs with greater responsibility. Despite the fact that women often possess equal or even higher levels of education and qualifications compared to men, these resources fail to translate into equal wages and career opportunities.

The in-depth interviews reinforced the quantitative findings, exposing everyday discriminatory practices: personal questions during interviews, the devaluation of women's leadership skills, and lower promotion rates. These experiences show that gender discrimination in Georgia is not merely a statistical disparity but an integral part of women's professional reality.

The findings directly contradict neoclassical theory, which explains gender inequality through individual choices (Becker, 1993). Instead, the results strongly support institutional and radical theories: women's opportunities are systematically restricted by stereotypes, organizational culture, and the "glass ceiling" (North, 1990; Morrison et al., 1987; Cotter et al., 2001).

International comparisons further underscore this picture: while the average gender pay gap in EU countries is 12%, in Georgia it is 20.9% (Eurostat, 2023). OECD experience demonstrates that pay transparency policies and mandatory gender audits effectively reduce inequality (OECD, 2021). The absence of such

mechanisms in Georgia remains one of the key structural challenges.

Thus, gender inequality in Georgia is not only a violation of social justice but also a significant obstacle to the country's economic development. The underutilization of women's professional potential limits national competitiveness and hinders sustainable economic growth.

Recommendations

The findings indicate that addressing gender inequality in Georgia requires **multi-level intervention**. Given the systemic nature of the problem, neither one-time regulations nor isolated organizational policies can resolve it. Instead, coordinated action among the state, the private sector, and the academic/research community is essential. Recommendations are presented at three main levels:

- **At the state level**
- **Pay transparency policies:** Companies should be legally required to publish gender pay gap data on a regular basis.
- **Gender audits:** Following OECD experience, mandatory audits should be introduced in medium and large enterprises.
- **Strengthening legal mechanisms:** Simplify legal procedures for proving discrimination to provide women with more effective instruments of protection.
- **Strategic commitments:** National strategies should set measurable targets, such as reducing the gender pay gap from 20.9% to below 10% within a decade.
- **At the organizational level**
- **Fair pay policies:** Companies should adopt and enforce the principle of "equal pay for equal work."
- **HR training and awareness-raising:** Recruiters and HR managers should undergo mandatory anti-discrimination training.
- **Women's leadership programs:** Mentoring and coaching initiatives should be implemented to support women's advancement.
- **Transforming organizational culture:** Work environments should ensure that women feel comfortable voicing opinions and participating in decision-making.
- **At the academic and research level**
- **Sector-specific studies:** In-depth research is needed in key sectors such as finance, technology, and agriculture.
- **Employers' perspectives:** Studies should explore employers' attitudes and stereotypes regarding gender roles.
- **International comparative analysis:** Georgia's data should be systematically compared with other post-Soviet countries to identify shared patterns and best practices.

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